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Similarities and differences in the evolution of VET in Hungary and Poland 1989–2022

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Abstract

The article takes a multi-pronged approach to study the main challenges in vocational education and training (VET) faced by Hungary and Poland in the transformation of their economies in 1989. The development of VET is examined in light of different development paths, ongoing criticism, declining prestige, dual training, governance, and VET research. We review the lessons learned from the changes experienced in the two countries as a result of the COVID-19 epidemic and examine the prospects for the current situation regarding VET in light of the recent Cedefop VET scenarios.

Keywords

vocational education and training (VET), transformation, new scenarios, Central and Eastern Europe, Hungary, Poland

1 Introduction

The social and economic changes initiated at the turn of the 1990s had a great impact on the education systems of the former socialist countries. Although different privatization policies had been employed, the discontinuation of corporate internships and training workshops, tackling mass unemployment, and organizing retraining courses for those affected became an extraordinary task for initial VET and adult education in all former socialist countries. ‘In the last few decades, economic liberalization has spread across the former socialist region at a higher pace than in the world ...’ (Porčnik, 2019). Accession to the EU, the economic crisis and recently the COVID-19 pandemic have changed provisions for VET in all countries of Central and Eastern Europe (CEE).

In the light of the conditions mentioned above, in our study, we present some of the most important elements of the development and changes in Hungarian and Polish vocational education and training from the period after the 1989 regime change to the present day. To compare the two vocational education and training systems, we have selected some aspects which we believe to be of great importance for the evolution of VET in both countries.

It is crucial to note that we try to place VET, not in isolation but, as far as possible within the scope of this report, in a broader context. We are convinced that vocational education and training, because of its broad economic and social determinants, cannot be examined and judged

without knowledge and study of the complex and diverse systems of influences and interests involved.¹

The selection of topics is based on recent study (Benke & Rachwał, 2022) comparing VET in the two countries, extended by some new topics. The social and economic changes initiated at the turn of the 1990s had a great impact on the education systems of the former socialist countries. Poland and Hungary were ranked among the most successful implementers of reforms at the beginning of regime change (Kozenkow, 2011). On the other hand, the economic structure (Kilar & Rachwał, 2014), the nature of post-regime privatization, and VET policy differ in the two countries, making them interesting cases to compare.

2 Methodology

The method of our research is literature review, based on a critical analysis of national literature. Our article uses a multi-faceted approach to present the major challenges to VET that Hungary and Poland have been facing during the transformation of their economic systems in 1989 and joining the EU in 2004. The evolution of VET is examined according to different paths, continuous criticism towards VET, its declining prestige, the introduction of dual training and governance. We also look at recent changes as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic and the current situation in the light of VET scenarios recently developed by Cedefop (2020); (Benke & Rachwał, 2022).

3 Main findings

3.1 Different paths in secondary level - General upper secondary education vs. vocational education

After the change of the regime VET was developing differently in Hungary and Poland in the 1990s. The Polish education system became more 'general', while the Hungarian retained a relatively strong VET which later became increasingly practice-oriented. In Poland around 1990, the liquidation and closure of vocational schools took place on a larger scale than in Hungary. However, focusing on upper secondary education, according to data, by 2021 upper secondary general education had become more popular in Hungary compared to Poland. This may suggest that Polish secondary vocational institutions with well-equipped school workshops may have been recently more attractive for VET candidates than Hungarian institutions. Despite the decline, the number of Polish VET students (more than 660 000) is still by far the highest in Central and Eastern Europe, and among the highest in the EU.

3.2 Low performance - Continuous criticism towards VET

There has been a continuous criticism of VET in both countries for decades, the essence of which is that VET does not meet the needs of the economy.

In both countries, policy highlights the indispensability of general knowledge in a turbulent, often unpredictable economic environment. The simplification, considering VET mostly from a short-term labour market perspective, forgetting its complexity as a system with several external factors, has weakened its prestige and compromised its quality, especially in the lower 'branch' of VET. A recent study draws attention to the risk that leaders or representatives of firms and companies often believe that short-term labour shortages are the

¹ Our opinions are based on scientific publications and other official research findings and do not necessarily reflect official views.

main obstacle to their future development while suggesting a reduction in the emphasis on basic skills in the curriculum (Munkácsy & Scharle, 2021).

In Hungary, the employment rate of recent VET graduates at 86.3% in 2019, exceeding the EU average (79.1%). However, vocational schools' limited general education content has been problematized (Horn, 2014; Mártonfi, 2019). Together with the concentration of students with low socioeconomic status, explains the heavy deficit in basic skills measured in PISA and high drop-out rates: in 2016 in the lower level of VET drop-out rate was 15.3%, against 6.5% in the higher-level form, and 1.1% in general upper-secondary schools (Varga, 2018). In Hungary the impact of pupils' socioeconomic background on education is the strongest in the EU. The impact of school type is also very significant, reflecting early selection in secondary education (European Commission, 2017; Bükki, 2019).

Although the early school leaving (ESL) rate in Poland is relatively low (5%), the problems associated with its consequences are a concern for researchers. Students who early leave school feel marginalised, and are thus marginalised regarding their life chances (social, cultural, and personal), which may lead to their social exclusion, poverty and helplessness even transferred to the next generations. (Tomaszewska-Pekala, Marchlik & Wrona, 2015).

3.3 The governance of VET

The governance of VET (Lassnig et.al 2018) is highly centralised in both countries, but in Poland not as strongly as in Hungary, because local and regional governments are still responsible for running VET schools. The economic and labour market relevance of VET is an absolute priority (Benke, 2019). The social aspects of VET have been neglected and little attention is being paid to recognising that transmission of knowledge about democracy alone is not enough for students to become democratically-minded citizens (Csapó, 2000). Partnership, including cooperation with social partners, and socialisation have been unresolved challenges in VET development work for decades, especially in Hungary.

From September 2020, important changes have started in the Hungarian VET system. One of the a major element in the transformation of the Hungarian vocational education and training system was the radical reduction of the number of occupations by about two-thirds, the introduction of training outcome requirements that substantially transformed the subject system and had not previously been applied in vocational education and training, and the introduction of new curricula and programme requirements. All of these changes have triggered a complete overhaul of the content of VET institutions (centres and member schools) (Györgyi, 2019).

Similarly, in Poland, as a result of the education reforms, the list of professions was changed and new vocational training programs for various qualifications were introduced. In Poland the core curricula for both general and VET have been changed many times (Nowak, 2017; Rachwał et al., 2018). This situation is subject to widespread criticism as reforms have been implemented without a thorough assessment of the effects of previous reforms. Following the typology developed by Pilz (2016), the Polish VET system is characterised by Reegård and Dębowski (2020) as a state-regulated, highly stratified, highly standardised system, with low levels of experience of labour market practice. The lack of teachers of vocational subjects will become even more acute in the coming years (Dolinska et al., 2019; Schröder et al., 2020).

VET governance at different levels constantly raises important questions in both countries. In Hungary the topic focuses on the issue of centralization and decentralization, while in Poland it is around the issue of rebuilding VET and adapt to the modern requirements of the labour market (Kurek, Rachwał, 2012; Melnarowicz. & Melnarowicz, 2017; Kust, 2020).

3.4 The prestige of VET

There is a close relationship between knowledge conveyed by initial VET and the vulnerable social situation of young people leaving VET (Marhuenda-Fluixá, 2017). The lower the social

status of the profession, the lower the prestige of the school and the more vulnerable are its students on the labour market.

In Poland, large state-owned enterprises were closed in the 1990s, so were the vocational schools functioning alongside them. Moreover, VET seemed to be too expensive and held no future for Poland's economic development (Dębowski & Stęchły, 2015). Due to the lack of investment and modernisation, VET could not provide the skills needed for emerging high-tech industries following the influx of foreign investors and the development of new private enterprises. In this situation, many young people believed that VET had no future. The interest of candidates and the prestige of vocational schools began to decline (Kurek & Rachwał, 2012; Pasierbek, 2011), which is still largely visible today. Reegård and Dębowski (2020) confirm this conclusion – according to them VET suffers from a disparity of esteem compared to academic education, despite governmental activities to change its negative image.

The prestige of VET is still a current theme in Poland. The amendment to the Law on School Education Act's target in Poland is to improve the prestige of initial vocational education, mostly through improving the quality and effectiveness of VET in schools and other institutions. The implementation of the changes started in the school year 2019/2020. OECD (2020).

The prestige of VET in the light of enrolment data has long been a critical point of Hungarian VET. Within the framework of the market economy, which replaced the state of the working class, the situation of manual wage workers has inevitably changed, and the prestige of VET preparing for this work has deteriorated even more than before. The government introduced measures that seek to make VET more attractive to young people through various 'facilitation measures' such as reducing general education, and the 'simplified' content and delivery conditions for VET (Horn, 2014; Kunert, 2016; Mártonfi, 2019). In Hungary, the prestige of VET has not improved despite measures taken by governments. The curtailment and centralization of the decision-making powers of school directors did not produce the desired results in Hungary, where the previously flexible, relatively freely interoperable horizontal system has become rigid and impenetrable (Mártonfi, 2019).

The changing pattern of parents' and students' decisions to continue their education, which is contrary to the government's intentions: since the radical reduction of the general education content of school-based vocational education, interest in general secondary schools has increased and interest in vocational education and training institutions has decreased. As the government is making considerable efforts to reverse the trend towards further education and to channel a larger share of students towards vocational education, there is no question of rationalising the network of vocational education and training institutions and reducing their redundant capacity. However, the overcapacity in vocational schools has been almost 'catastrophic': today, just over half of the places in technicums and just over a third of the places in vocational schools are being used (Ercse & Radó, 2019).

A further important aspect of the demand for university diplomas is that the wage advantage of Hungarian university graduates over secondary school graduates is quite outstanding in Europe. Another problem is that the Hungarian system is highly selective already at the point of entry to primary school. Even after 4th and 6th grades, there are already pathways out of the integrated education system into grammar schools. These circumstances all contribute to the stagnation of the low prestige of vocational education.

In Hungary, for many students, the vocational school appears as 'the last chance' (Makó, 2016). In Poland, they are called 'the schools of last resort'.

3.5 Dual training

The two countries appear to be in different positions over dual training. In Hungary, based on the experience gained, more critical opinions were expressed by researchers and trade unions,

especially regarding long-term effects, like the decline in VET students' theoretical and general knowledge (Hajdu et al., 2015; Fazekas et al., 2020). Additionally, different government policy measures did not significantly influence the willingness of companies to provide practical training for VET students. On the Polish side, the idea of developing a non-German type of dual training has emerged and opinions are more positive. However, schools nowadays seem to play a more important role in training students than companies, and the fact that there have been significant developments in school workshops, have also supported the renewed attractiveness of VET for young people.

The interest of companies in training differs widely between the two countries. In Hungary, until the end of 2021, for many decades, companies that did not undertake to train apprentices had to pay into the vocational training fund to ensure a more equal financial burden. We assume that the low financial interest of companies in investing in training, similarly their high interest in avoiding costs, is one of the reasons for the low participation of Polish companies in apprenticeships.

One of the survey results shows that employers are set on increasing the number of hours of students' practical vocational training in the workplace but are reluctant to undertake more costly and more demanding forms of cooperation with schools, like participating in vocational exams, training teachers or providing equipment for school workshops (Maleszyk, 2017). However, in Poland, due to the systematically decreasing unemployment rates in the years 2015-2021, enterprises are increasingly starting to look for opportunities to cooperate with vocational schools and they are increasingly willing to accept apprenticeships. In this way, they hope to attract employees in the future. It should be noted that additional training in enterprises is also an important form of vocational education for adults. As research shows, vocational training programs are particularly developed in the branches of international enterprises located in Poland (Tobolska, 2016). The cooperation of employers with vocational schools is one of the most important elements affecting the quality of education, in the course of various VET reforms in Poland, efforts were made to create mechanisms that would facilitate such cooperation (Kust, 2020).

3.6 Research

Research on VET in Hungary and Poland has only recently received more attention with a stronger critical voice. It had deteriorated strongly after the regime change and practically fell out of sight in sociological research in education (Kozma, 2021). Likewise, many forums for debate among VET actors disappeared. In this sense, our paper would like to support to re-establish scholarly informed debates among VET stakeholders. We assume and hope that the examples of our countries can provide interesting lessons for researching VET evolution in other former socialist countries, and maybe for all those facing similar challenges in our globalised world.

The small scale of VET research in Hungary is focused on the labour market perspective, with very little attention paid to the study of the losers from technical progress, the long-term laggards (Benke & Rachwał, 2022).

Among the small number of Hungarian vocational education and training research projects, the MTA²-supported 'Subject Pedagogical Research Programme', which is conducted in the framework of the BME³ in international research cooperation, is of great importance. This research develops the process of open curriculum development in VET by involving enterprising teacher students and teachers. In this way, research constitutes an important

² MTA = Hungarian Academy of Sciences

³ BME = Budapest University of Technology and Economics

element of innovation in the training of teachers involved in vocational education and training. The research and development work that had already begun has been given a strong impetus by the recent radical transformation of the VET system, which has created the imperativeness and opportunity for methodological change and research and development (Benedek, 2021). Interdisciplinary approaches in VET research (and development) are rare in both countries, as is VET research on the issues of ‘citizenship’ and ‘empowerment’. However, in the future, greater consideration of non-economic and non-market aspects may create new avenues and purposes for VET concerning social innovation. In this respect, the results of a survey in which nearly 90% of VET experts in Hungary stated that secondary VET institutions could play an important role in the life of local communities beyond teaching, was promising (Benke, 2016).

4 Conclusions

Polish and Hungarian VET are characterised by a continuous search for a new path. However, it seems in 2023 that, partly because of the COVID pandemic, the increasing level of uncertainty about the prospects for economies and the permanent skills shortages in many occupations will continue to dominate short-term VET policies in both countries. It is questionable how these circumstances will influence and determine the willingness of policymakers to turn towards more flexible, less economy-driven, and more ‘humanistic’ forms of VET.

As in Hungary, in Poland the situation in VET in the times of the COVID pandemic depended a lot on the specific sector, to what extent it was vulnerable to the crisis and whether it was affected by decisions concerning lockdowns. However, it seems that in those sectors, professions with strong and well-equipped workshops in schools could face the crisis under less dramatic conditions compared to those who had only or mostly training placements in companies. It seems that school workshops in certain conditions can serve as a lifeline during short-term crises.

Scenario research organised by Cedefop, gives rise to many ideas for the future. The question is whether the ‘Plural’ model, opening up to lifelong learning, can open up new horizons for secondary vocational education and training in building links with local societies and local economies (Benke, forthcoming). And as the new vocational education and training scenarios put dual training in a new light (Markowitsch & Bjørnåvold, 2022), an exciting challenge is how to reconcile the interests of companies with the ‘Plural Model’. Extrapolating past developments into the future would suggest in both countries either the ‘Distinctive’ or ‘Marginalised’ (according to Cedefop, 2020) scenario to materialise. We assume that learning about the scenarios and broadly discussing them could make a positive contribution to future development processes in VET in both Hungary and Poland.

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